

Teaching through Entry Test & Summarization - An Effective Classroom Teaching Model in Higher Education Training

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ABSTRACT

Systematic teaching through long time tested model will certainly improve the effectiveness of teaching-learning process in higher education. Teaching through Entry Test & Summarization is an effective model named 'Aithal model of effective classroom teaching' in Higher Education Training developed by Prof. Aithal combines both positive and negative motivation and integrated into a best practice. According to this model each class of one hour duration starts with silent prayer for one minute to recall the career objective or goal of individual students. As an entry test a set of questions on the topic discussed in the previous class will be displayed on the board. In the mean time students will get time to think the right answer, while the attendance is being taken. Students will be randomly picked to answer the entry test questions. The appreciation works as a positive motivation. After the teaching session, 2 to 3 students randomly picked are asked to summarize the class. The summarization opportunity for the students alerts the students throughout the class writing down the gist of the session and concentrate in the topic discussed in the class. The readiness in right answer can avoid possible shame thereby act as a negative motivation during summarization.

Keywords- *Effective teaching model, Quality in higher education, Aithal model of effective classroom teaching.*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching is the central activity in education system and Teacher is the critical figure in a student's journey through higher education. A teacher can be admirable in his students community due to his personality, characters, inspiring ability and innovative teaching style. A best teacher inspires the students and support to create new ideas and contributes the develops competencies in his students. Every teacher is boss in his class and has to take over the control of the class while teaching due to his teaching and class controlling style. A teacher can be excellent only if he plans the class properly, delivers the class with confidence by having

knowledge, skills and experience in the topic. Moreover, an innovative teacher uses variety of classroom techniques to inspire and attract students to create interest in the subject. Teaching a topic/subject will be meaningful and reaches its objective only if the students understand the concept/technique, able to apply it for practical problems and able to discover new opportunities/ideas. Teaching in higher education institution involves using a variety of methods and tools to ensure that each student is fully engaged in learning. This includes exploring new ideas in teaching, sharpening practices that are effective and broadening the use of technology. Systematic teaching through long time tested model will certainly improve the effectiveness of teaching-learning process in higher education. In this paper, a new long time tested model of teaching is presented. This model confirms the student involvement in the discussion either positive motivation or negative motivation.

NEW CLASSROOM TEACHING MODEL

Teaching through Entry Test & Summarization is an effective model in Higher Education Training named '*Aithal effective classroom teaching model*' developed by Prof. Aithal combines both positive and negative motivation and integrated into a best practice. According to this model each class of one hour/ one and half hour duration is organized as follows :

- (1) Starts with *silent prayer* for one minute to recall the career objective or goal of individual students.
- (2) After the silent prayer an entry test is conducted. In *entry test*, a set of questions on the topic discussed in the previous class will be displayed on the board.
- (3) In the mean time students will get time to think the right answer, while the attendance is being taken. Students will be randomly picked to answer the entry test questions. The appreciation works as a positive motivation.
- (4) The planned topic for the class will be discussed/presented using *suitable teaching method* by choosing appropriate pedagogy, and learning techniques.
- (5) After the teaching session, 2 to 3 students randomly picked are asked to *summarize* the class. The summarization opportunity for the students alerts the students throughout the class writing down the gist of the session and concentrate in the topic discussed in the class. The readiness in right answer can avoid possible shame thereby act as a negative motivation during summarization. The flow chart diagram of this model is shown in Fig. 1.

MERITS OF THE MODEL

An effective classroom teaching model developed by the author consists of the plan of action to handle one hour or one period class in a classroom for a given subject mainly for higher education institution. This model consists of *silent prayer* as the first step to recall the life goal of every student and reminding it in every class so that students will be alert about his responsibility and maintains self control through focused

mind towards the discussion topic of the class. Through *entry test* as second step, all students will recall whatever they studied in last class and with both positive and negative motivation, tries to answer the questions and subsequently be ready for today's class. Parallely, teacher calls attendance by name instead of roll numbers (which is common practice, the students will have proud of attending the class because every student like his name to be called in the class. Moreover, teacher can remember the name of all students easily and hence can avoid proxy attendance in the class. The time lapsed to call attendance is not wasted and all students will be busy in finding/recalling answers to entry test questions displayed on screen/board. All students will busy is finding answers to entry questions because the answer will be asked by any two or three students by picking up them randomly so that all students will be alert in finding answer to the question as third step. Once the suitable answers are obtained by the students, in the fourth step, the teacher will announce the topic of the class as per given in Session-wise teaching plan of the curriculum.

Fig. 1 : Flow chart diagram of 'Aithal Model of Effective Classroom Teaching.

Depending on the topic and the subject for discussion the teacher will follow suitable teaching method. All the students will note down main points discussed in the class for summarization purpose. At the end of the session, as fifth step, the teacher will pick any two students randomly to summarize the discussed topic on that class. In higher education classes, since students are matured and competitive, they try to present the summery in an attractive manner effectively to maintain their status in the peer group. This makes them to

be focused towards the class by noting down the main points of the discussion. Hence this teaching - learning model is very effective to keep students alert by reminding their goal in life and makes them focused in the class both physically and mentally so that students will completely involve in the class discussions and the purpose of students, teachers and higher education system is achieved. This also lead to 100 % result with distinctions and first class.

TEACHING METHODS USED IN THE MODEL

Some of the teaching methods used in third stage of the model are mentioned below :

(a) Concept based learning :

Concept-based instruction overcomes the fact-based, rote-oriented nature of standardized curriculum. If curriculum is not organized conceptually, by means of knowledge and resources teach how to generate ideas and deep understanding, not test items.

(b) Project based learning :

Teaching defined set of methods associated with high-quality PBL. These methods include developing a focused question, using solid, well crafted performance assessments, allowing for multiple solutions, enlisting community resources, and choosing engaging, meaningful themes for projects. PBL offers the best method we have presently for combining inquiry with accountability, and should be part of every teacher's repertoire.

(c) Distinguish concepts from critical information: Preparing students for tests is part of the job. But they need information for a more important reason: To innovate, they need to know something. The craft precedes the art. Find the right blend between open-ended inquiry and direct instruction.

(d) Teaching skills along with knowledge : Innovation and 21st century skills are closely related. Soft skills such as collaboration or critical thinking, to focus on throughout the year. Incorporate them into lessons. Use detailed rubrics to assess and grade the skills.

(e) Forming teams, not groups : Innovation now emerges from teams and networks—and we can teach students to work collectively and become better collective thinkers. Group work is common, but *team* work is rare. Some tips: Use specific methods to form teams; assess teamwork and work ethic; facilitate high quality interaction through protocols and critique; teach the cycle of revision; and expect students to reflect critically on both ongoing work and final products.

(f) Use thinking tools. Hundreds of interesting, thought provoking tools exist for thinking through problems, sharing insights, finding solutions, and encouraging divergent solutions. Use Big Think tools or the Visible Thinking Routines developed at Harvard's Project Zero.

(g) Use creativity tools : Industry uses a set of cutting edge tools to stimulate creativity and innovation. As described in books such as Game-storming or Beyond Words, the tools include playful games and visual exercises that can easily be used in the classroom.

(h) Reward discovery : Innovation is mightily discouraged by our system of assessment, which rewards the mastery of known information. Step up the reward system by using rubrics with a blank column to acknowledge and reward innovation and creativity.

(i) Make reflection part of the lesson : Because of the coverage imperative, the tendency is to move on quickly from the last chapter and begin the next chapter. But reflection is necessary to anchor learning and stimulate deeper thinking and understanding. There is no innovation without rumination.

(j) Be innovative yourself : This is the kicker, because innovation requires the willingness to fail, a focus on fuzzy outcomes rather than standardized measures, and the bravery to resist the system's emphasis on strict accountability. But the reward is a kind of liberating creativity that makes teaching exciting and fun, engages students, and—most critical—helps students find the passion and resources necessary to design a better life for themselves and others.

(k) Generating new Ideas : In any subject based on concepts and models discussed, generate new idea to overcome drawbacks of the system by discussing possible new ideas related to the problem. Spending 5 to 10 minutes on problem solution or identifying new application through innovative idea generation session.

(l) Giving Assignment in every class : Poising challenging assignments to the students and make them to apply their mind and time to find a solution and to collect further information to enhance their knowledge and skills is always expected at higher education teaching system.

(m) Additional Hot information in every class : The teacher collects day to day news and upto date information and present it to the students along with announced curriculum of the course. This method updates the students knowledge in a given area irrespective of the quality of University curriculum.

(n) Blending teaching facilities : Use of PPT presentation, video clips, Black Board writing as per requirement, giving exercises in the class, discussion with students, Showing at least one video clip per day related to the subject, Teaching according to pre-announced session teaching plan, Involving every student in the class, Teaching through discussion & interaction, Information related to further studies & sources on the topic, Using audio & video business cases & Case lets, Using illustrations, Motivating through inspiring and Challenging, Simulation exercises, Student Presentation, in-basket exercises etc. makes students to understand the concept.

CONCLUSIONS

Teaching through Entry Test & Summarization is an effective model named '*Aithal model of effective classroom teaching*' in Higher Education Training developed by Prof. Aithal combines both positive and negative motivation and integrated into a best practice. According to this model each class of one hour duration starts with silent prayer for one minute to recall the career objective or goal of individual students. As an entry test a set of questions on the topic discussed in the previous class will be displayed on the board. In the mean time students will get time to think the right answer, while the attendance is being taken.

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